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Magnetic covalent hybrid of graphitic carbon nitride and graphene oxide as an efficient catalyst support for immobilization of Pd nanoparticles

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Abstract

For the first time a magnetic carbon based hybrid catalyst, Pd@g-C₃N₄-Fe-GO, is prepared through covalent conjugation of magnetic graphitic carbon nitride and graphene oxide followed by incorporation of Pd nanoparticles. First, the formation of the catalyst was confirmed via XRD, TG, BET, TEM, FTIR, ICP and VSM analyses and then its catalytic activity for promoting Suzuki and Sonogashira coupling reactions under mild reaction condition was investigated. To elucidate whether hybridization of two carbon materials could improve the catalytic activity, the catalytic activity of the catalyst was compared with the control catalysts (Pd@g-C₃N₄-GO, Pd@g-C₃N₄-Fe, Pd@Fe-GO, Pd@g-C₃N₄, Pd@GO and the GO/g-C₃N₄ physical hybrid). Moreover, the role of magnetic nanoparticles in the catalytic performance was confirmed. Notably, the catalytic activities of the catalyst and the control sample prepared via physical hybridization of two carbon materials were compared to confirm the

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effect of covalent conjugation on the catalytic activity. Moreover, the study of the substituent effect of p-substituted phenyl iodides was considered by

Hammett plot, which revealed a beneficial effect of electron-withdrawing side groups for the Csingle bondC coupling reaction. Finally, the recyclability of Pd@g-C₃N₄-Fe-GO as well as leaching of Pd and magnetic nanoparticles was studied.

Keywords: Graphitic carbon nitride, Graphene oxide, Magnetic catalyst, Coupling reactions, Pd nanoparticles